

epsilon-delta proofs for limits in a simplified way

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1 Abstract

In this paper, i first give an intuitive introduction to logic used for mathematical proofs and then proceed to formulating the epsilon-delta definition for limits which turn the informal idea of 'approaching' a limit into rigorously defined mathematics. These epsilon-delta definitions can then be used to deductively prove the existence of a limit. This all only sounds difficult (and cool), no advanced mathematics is required to get a gist of it. The essence of pre-calculus, a strong understanding of algebra, and an open mind would be enough to not only understand it but also extend it.

2 Introduction to Logic in Mathematics

A proof, as the name suggests, refers to the idea of knowing something with a high degree of certainty. A conjecture is a statement that can either be true or false, and we can use different kinds of logic to prove or disprove a conjecture. In mathematics and physics almost all the time, the following two kinds of logical reasoning are used.

2.1 Deductive reasoning

In deductive reasoning, we construct a chain of facts that we already know to be true, in a proper way as to avoid any fallacies. Almost all of pure mathematics is based on deductive reasoning, and it is the most powerful line of reasoning in a sense that if a deductive proof is valid, it guarantees that the conjecture it was meant to prove is 100% correct, provided the facts used to construct the deductive argument are 100% correct. Deductive arguments can be said to take general facts and create specific solutions from them. Consider the following example:

Conjecture: tobi has a tail.

proof:

fact number 1: all cats have tails.

fact number 2: tobi is a cat.

hence using the facts 1 and 2, it can be deductively proved that the provided conjecture is true i.e. tobi indeed has a tail. This is a basic example of a proof by deductive reasoning.

2.2 Inductive reasoning

For the inductive reasoning, we have to abandon the thrill of certainty and move to the realm of probabilities. Contrary to deductive reasoning, here we take a fact that we know to be true in a specific situation and generalize it. A fact that is certainly true in a specific situation is *probably* true in a general one. Consider the following example:

Conjecture: tobi will probably eat tomorrow.

proof:

fact number 1: tobi ate yesterday and all the days before till his birth.

fact number 2: tobi is a living thing and needs food to stay alive.

hence using the above two facts we can inductively say that the provided conjecture is true i.e. tobi will *probably* eat tomorrow.

Now, some of you might not be satisfied as to why it's *probably* true, why not certainly true? to give you some counter-examples, tobi might die today. Although the chances of it happening are slim but non-zero nevertheless. There is also a non-zero chance that due to some undiscovered phenomenon, tobi might become immortal and never need food again. The possibilities are endless, and just a single counter-example with a non-zero probability is enough to convert *certainly* to *probably*. All of the physics is based on inductive reasoning. We create and test the laws of the universe here on earth and then assume that the same laws will *probably* work anywhere else in the universe.

3 The Epsilon-Delta Definition

3.1 functions

Before we proceed to defining the limits, we need to have a strong grip of what functions are. To put it in the most straight-forward way, a (single-variable) function is a mathematical object that takes in an input and gives out an output. usually the input is denoted by x and the output by y or $f(x)$. Consider the following example:

$$f(x) = x^2 + 2x + 1 \tag{1}$$

At $x = 1$, the value of $y = f(1) = 1 + 2 + 1 = 4$ and so on. Of course this is an oversimplified definition but should be good enough to provide the necessary intuition.

3.2 limits

Consider a function $f(x)$. At the point $x = a$, the value of the function $y = f(a)$ equals L . Now assuming the function is continuous, as the input x gets closer and closer to a , the output $y = f(x)$ gets closer and closer to L . This idea of getting closer and closer to a certain value is captured in a limit. It is notated as follows:

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a} f(x) = L \tag{2}$$

Read as "the limit as x approaches a equals L ". Note that x never actually reaches a , it just ever keeps getting closer and closer to a . Some of you might have noticed a problem with this, which is that this idea of a limit is loose. How do we express this idea of ever getting closer to a value using

rigorous mathematics? We do just that through the epsilon-delta definition of a limit.

Figure 1: plot of a continuous function $y = f(x) = x$ created using the manim library in python3.

Let's say we have a continuous function $y = f(x)$ such that the value of the function equals L at the point $x = a$ i.e. $f(a) = L$. Now let's define ϵ to be an indivisibly small but finite number such that there is no number x that satisfies $a < x < a + \epsilon$. Ofcourse this condition is too idealistic, but taking a very small number for ϵ would work just fine. The values of the function at $a + \epsilon$ and $a - \epsilon$ equal $L + \delta$ and $L - \delta$ respectively as evident from the diagram above. Mathematically, they can be written as follows.

$$f(a + \epsilon) = L + \delta \tag{3}$$

$$f(a - \epsilon) = L - \delta \tag{4}$$

By defining these constants this way, we are essentially saying that as long as a value of x lies in between $a - \epsilon$ and $a + \epsilon$, the value of y is guaranteed to lie in the range $L - \delta$ to $L + \delta$.

$$a - \epsilon < x < a + \epsilon \implies L - \delta < y < L + \delta \tag{5}$$

The above inequalities, by using some basic algebra, can be written in the following modular forms:

$$|x - a| < \epsilon \implies |y - L| < \delta \tag{6}$$

which means that as long as the distance between x and a is less than ϵ , the distance between y and L will be less than δ . This rigorous definition is much more convenient to work with compared to the loose idea of 'approaching'. Now instead, we can just say that a limit exists if the above condition is satisfied.

3.3 the epsilon-delta proof for limits

In the above definition of a limit, some of you might have noticed a relation. For any smooth function, the limit must converge to a single point. For the limit to converge, as ϵ gets smaller, δ must get smaller as well.

$$\epsilon \propto \delta \quad (7)$$

$$\epsilon = K\delta \quad (8)$$

If, for a specific limit, we can show that the inequalities in (6) are true from equation (8), the limit can be said to exist. Let's now apply all this abstraction to a few concrete examples.

3.3.1 the first example

Conjecture: the limit $\lim_{x \rightarrow 2} x^2 + 2x + 2 = 10$.

Proof:

Comparing this with the general equations in (2) and (6), we get that $a = 2$, $f(x) = x^2 + 2x + 2$, $L = 10$. If we can mathematically show that $|x - 2| < \epsilon$ and $|x^2 + 2x + 2 - 10| = |x^2 + 2x - 8| < \delta$ from $\epsilon = K\delta$, the limit would be said to exist. Let's do some algebra now:

$$|x^2 + 2x - 8| < \delta \quad (9)$$

$$|x^2 + 2x + 1^2 - 1^2 - 8| < \delta \quad (10)$$

$$|(x + 1)^2 - 1 - 8| < \delta \quad (11)$$

$$|(x + 1)^2 - (3)^2| < \delta \quad (12)$$

$$|(x + 1 - 3)(x + 1 + 3)| < \delta \quad (13)$$

$$|x - 2||x + 4| < \delta \quad (14)$$

$$|x - 2| < \frac{\delta}{|x + 4|} \quad (15)$$

The term $|x - 2|$ also appears in the ϵ inequality so we made it the subject from above. This gives us a hint about what the equation connecting ϵ and δ could be. Let's make the following assumption and see if it holds or not.

$$\text{let } \epsilon = \frac{\delta}{|x + 4|} \text{ as } x \rightarrow 2, \frac{1}{|x + 4|} \rightarrow \frac{1}{6} = K \quad (16)$$

Now let's substitute this equation and see if it satisfies the inequalities that guarantee the existence of a limit.

$$|x - 2| < \epsilon \quad (17)$$

$$|x - 2| < \frac{\delta}{|x + 4|} \quad (18)$$

$$|x - 2||x + 4| < \delta \quad (19)$$

$$|x^2 + 2x - 8| < \delta \quad (20)$$

Which is indeed the second inequality! this relation of ϵ and δ satisfies the inequalities hence it can be deductively said that the provided limit exists. If the limit did not exist, no equation connecting ϵ and δ would satisfy the inequalities.

3.3.2 the second example

Conjecture: the limit $\lim_{x \rightarrow 3} x^2 + x - 1 = 11$.

Proof:

The limit would be said to exist if:

$$|x - 3| < \epsilon \implies |x^2 + x - 1 - 11| = |x^2 + x - 12| < \delta \quad (21)$$

$$|x - 3||x + 4| < \delta \quad (22)$$

$$|x - 3| < \frac{\delta}{|x + 4|} \quad (23)$$

$$\text{let } \epsilon = \frac{\delta}{|x + 4|}, \text{ as } x \rightarrow 3, \frac{1}{|x + 4|} \rightarrow \frac{1}{7} = K \quad (24)$$

$$(25)$$

Now let's see if this assumed equation connecting ϵ and δ satisfies the both inequalities that guarantee the existence of a limit.

$$|x - 3| < \epsilon \quad (26)$$

$$|x - 3| < \frac{\delta}{|x + 4|} \quad (27)$$

$$|x - 3||x + 4| < \delta \quad (28)$$

$$|x^2 + x - 12| < \delta \quad (29)$$

Abracadabra! the value of ϵ in-terms of δ we assumed converted the first inequality to the second inequality i.e. satisfied the both inequalities, hence it has been deductively proved that the provided limit exists.

4 Conclusion

Some of you might wonder why cant we just use the reasoning that as we put closer and closer values of x into the calculator, the values of y get closer and closer to L . The only thing we can conclude from this is that the limit is *probably* true. We cannot test every single value of x as it approaches a certain value. Using the epsilon-delta proof we did above, we can say with a 100% certainty whether a certain limit exists or not. Now, how would we extend this idea of epsilon-delta proof to trigonometric, exponential, and essentially every non-polynomial functions? well, we can derive a polynomial approximation for those functions using Taylor series and use the inductive reasoning that since the limit exists for the approximation, it would *probably* also exist for the function.

5 Works Used

[1] Thomas, George Brinton, et al. Thomas' calculus. Addison-Wesley, 2005.

[2] Kelley, David. The art of reasoning: An introduction to logic and critical thinking. WW Norton & Company, 2013.